

BIANCA : A GENETIC ALGORITHM TO SOLVE LAMINATE DESIGN PROBLEMS

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ABSTRACT

The design of laminates with given properties is a subject of interest both in scientific research and in engineering applications, and many authors deal with different aspects of this large domain. Anyway, there is not any unique or unified approach to this subject and in the literature we can find different kinds of problem formulations combined with different solving methods.

In this paper, we show how the application of the polar representation method for plane elasticity can give a unique formulation to a large number of problems in the design of composite laminates. Our formulation has the form of a classic structural optimization problem, with a unique objective function and multiple possible constraints.

Moreover, our formulation takes into account a large range of problems, in order to conceive laminates with many different design properties, such as:

- given symmetries for in- and out-of-plane elastic behaviors: orthotropy, R_0 -orthotropy, square-symmetry, isotropy;
- uncoupling;
- quasi-homogeneity;
- relative positions of axes of symmetry for in-plane and out-of-plane behaviors;
- given stiffness (Young's moduli and other constants);
- given strength;
- all possible combinations of these properties.

We consider the following laminate parameters as variables:

- characteristics of ply material, which may be different for each layer;
- ply orientation angles;
- laminate stacking sequence;
- number of layers.

In this paper, we present BIANCA, the genetic algorithm that we developed to solve all the problems listed before and many more, as well.

BIANCA is a versatile instrument for the design of composite laminates, because it is conceived to answer current engineering problems as well as academic questions. In particular, BIANCA allows the designer to choose among all the laminate parameters which ones are variable and which ones are to be fixed. Moreover, a large freedom is left in the choice of variation ranges for variable parameters, and designing laminates with discrete variable parameters is possible with BIANCA, as well as with continuous ones.

We describe the structure of BIANCA and we give some examples of laminates found as solutions to different design problems.

KEYWORDS : elastic design, optimization, polar method, genetic algorithm.

INTRODUCTION

Laminate design has been a domain of active research in the last decades, mainly for the increasing use of laminates in engineering applications. In this field, a state of the art [1] shows that there is not a unique nor a principal way to approach laminate design, and in the literature we can find different kinds of problem formulations combined with different solving methods [1]. Nevertheless, some general considerations can be done about laminates design: the most part of authors deal with the maximization of some mechanical properties, such as the stiffness or the strength, as well as the buckling load or the fundamental frequency, or the minimization of the weight under some mechanical constraints. Almost all the authors make some basic hypothesis about the laminate: generally, they consider symmetric stacking sequences, which automatically ensures uncoupling of the in- and out-of-plane behaviors, that is $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{O}$. In many cases, only some orientations are considered for the plies; typical is the case of balanced symmetric quasi-isotropic (orientations at 0° , $\pm 45^\circ$, 90°), cross-ply (0° , 90°) or angle-ply ($\alpha, -\alpha$) laminates, in order to have uncoupling and orthotropy of \mathbf{A} .

What seems to be a general rule is that laminate designers try to optimise some parameters of the plate considering that it has already some other, generally required, properties, such as orthotropy or uncoupling. To do this, they do not look for general solutions, but only for solutions belonging to a special class, to automatically ensure the desired property. This way of doing is in a sense a shortcut to solutions, especially for the computing aspects, but can lead to solutions which are optimal only in the chosen class of laminates but not globally. In this sense, Vannucci and Verchery, [2] and [3], have shown that the number of uncoupled symmetric laminates is very small compared with that of non-symmetric ones. So, looking for uncoupled laminates only in the class of symmetric plates can be very limiting.

Indeed, the design of general elastic properties of a laminate, such as isotropy, orthotropy or uncoupling, has not received by the scientists the same interest that they have reserved to the above mentioned problems. Nevertheless, some interesting works in this field can be found in literature, see for instance the fundamental contribution of Werren and Norris [4] on isotropy, the works of Fukunaga, [5], Paradies [6], Grédiac [7], Vannucci and Verchery [8] still on isotropy, those of Caprino and Crivelli-Visconti [9] and of Grédiac [10] on orthotropy, and the already cited Vannucci and Verchery, [2] and [3], on uncoupling and quasi-homogeneity.

In preceding works, the authors have reconsidered the problem of designing general properties of laminates, such as elastic symmetries, uncoupling, quasi-homogeneity and so on, and have proposed an original way to unify several of these problems which preserves the absolute generality of the approach: no kind of simplifying hypothesis is made, so general solutions can be found for a given problem.

In this paper, we briefly recall the unified approach to the design of a laminate with respect to its elastic symmetries and then we present BIANCA, the genetic algorithm that we developed to numerically solve this kind of problems. BIANCA is a versatile instrument for the design of composite laminates, as it is conceived to adapt to current engineering problems as well as to academic needs too. The paper ends with some numerical examples that show the effectiveness of the proposed genetic algorithm.

FORMULATION OF DESIGN PROBLEMS

Let us consider the following general problem: find the layer orientations δ_k of a n -ply laminate to obtain a given general elastic property, such as isotropy, orthotropy, uncoupling

and so on. To state the above problem, we introduce the quadratic form of the matrix \mathbf{H} , defined on the 18-dimensional space of the variables P_i :

$$I(P_k) = \mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{H} \mathbf{P} = H_{ij} P_i P_j, \quad i, j = 1, \dots, 18 \quad (1)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} P_1 &= \frac{\bar{T}_0}{h M}, \quad P_2 = \frac{\bar{T}_1}{h M}, \quad P_3 = \frac{\bar{R}_0}{h M}, \quad P_4 = \frac{\bar{R}_1}{h M}, \quad P_5 = \bar{\Phi}_0, \quad P_6 = \bar{\Phi}_1, \\ P_7 &= \frac{2 \hat{T}_0}{h^2 M}, \quad P_8 = \frac{2 \hat{T}_1}{h^2 M}, \quad P_9 = \frac{2 \hat{R}_0}{h^2 M}, \quad P_{10} = \frac{2 \hat{R}_1}{h^2 M}, \quad P_{11} = \hat{\Phi}_0, \quad P_{12} = \hat{\Phi}_1, \\ P_{13} &= \frac{12 \tilde{T}_0}{h^3 M}, \quad P_{14} = \frac{12 \tilde{T}_1}{h^3 M}, \quad P_{15} = \frac{12 \tilde{R}_0}{h^3 M}, \quad P_{16} = \frac{12 \tilde{R}_1}{h^3 M}, \quad P_{17} = \tilde{\Phi}_0, \quad P_{18} = \tilde{\Phi}_1. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The parameters $T_0, T_1, R_0, R_1, \Phi_0$ and Φ_1 are the so-called polar components of an elastic tensor in plane elasticity, introduced as early as 1979 by G. Verchery, see [11], [12] or also [3]. The symbols $\bar{\cdot}$, $\hat{\cdot}$ and $\tilde{\cdot}$ refer to tensors \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{D} respectively; M is a factor used to obtain non-dimensional variables. Several definitions are possible for M , provided that it is never zero; proper choices are means of layers characteristics quantities. Generally speaking, the quadratic form $I(P_k)$ depends upon all the mechanical and geometrical parameters of the laminate, [12] and [13], that is orientations, stacking sequence, the material and the thickness of the layers.

\mathbf{H} is a symmetric matrix of non-dimensional real numbers: the choice of its components H_{ij} determines the kind of problem to be treated; several choices are possible, and so several different problems can be stated in the same way, simply changing the H_{ij} . \mathbf{H} is positive semi-definite, and each problem can be stated as follows: find an absolute minimum of (1) for a given \mathbf{H} . As \mathbf{H} is positive semi-definite, these minimums are zero-valued. Clearly, to solve such a problem means to find a vector \mathbf{P} of P_k , that is the 18 polar components, that satisfy the above statement. A certain number of different and technically interesting problems are detailed in [12] and [13]; here, only some of these problems, particularly important, are considered, and the components H_{ij} are shown for each case. It must be said, anyway, that a larger number of problems, not always technically interesting, can be treated in the same way.

Before going on, we remark that a unique mathematical form has been given to several different problems of laminate design: the search for the minimum of a positive semi-definite form, which is a classic problem of structural optimization. The objective function (1) is not convex, since parameters P_k depend upon circular functions of the orientations, [12] and [13].

First of all, let us consider the search for uncoupled laminates; this problem can be stated as follows:

$$\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{O}; \quad I(P_k) = \sum_{i=7}^{10} P_i^2 = 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad H_{ii} = 1, \quad i = 7, \dots, 10. \quad (3)$$

If the laminate is composed by identical plies, it is automatically

$$P_7 = P_8 = 0, \quad (4)$$

so H_{77} and H_{88} are meaningless, that is they can be equally posed 0 or 1.

Another case of interest, is that of uncoupled laminates with **A** or **D** isotropic, which can be respectively stated as

$$I(P_k) = P_3^2 + P_4^2 + \sum_{i=7}^{10} P_i^2 = 0 \Rightarrow H_{ii} = 1, i = 3, 4, 7, 8, 9, 10; \quad (5)$$

$$I(P_k) = \sum_{i=7}^{10} P_i^2 + P_{15}^2 + P_{16}^2 = 0 \Rightarrow H_{ii} = 1, i = 7, 8, 9, 10, 15, 16. \quad (6)$$

In the same way, the very treated problem of fully isotropy, that is of the search for an uncoupled laminate with isotropic tensors **A** and **D**, can be stated:

$$I(P_k) = P_3^2 + P_4^2 + \sum_{i=7}^{10} P_i^2 + P_{15}^2 + P_{16}^2 = 0 \Rightarrow H_{ii} = 1, i = 3, 4, 7, 8, 9, 10, 15, 16. \quad (7)$$

Another interesting problem is that of an uncoupled laminate with square symmetric **A** and **D**, having in addition the same axes of symmetry. Now, the coincidence of the axes must be imposed; in the polar method, this can be easily done by setting $\bar{\Phi}_0 = \tilde{\Phi}_0$:

$$I(P_k) = P_4^2 + \sum_{i=7}^{10} P_i^2 + P_{16}^2 + (P_5 - P_{17})^2 = 0 \Rightarrow \quad (8)$$

$$H_{ii} = 1, i = 4, 5, 7, 8, 9, 10, 16, 17; \quad H_{517} = -1.$$

A general condition for quasi-homogeneity (that is to say, for having uncoupled laminates with equal elastic properties in bending and in extension) is the following one, [12] or [13]:

$$I(P_k) = (P_1 - P_{13})^2 + (P_2 - P_{14})^2 + (P_3 - P_{15})^2 +$$

$$+ (P_4 - P_{16})^2 + (P_5 - P_{17})^2 + (P_6 - P_{18})^2 +$$

$$+ P_7^2 + P_8^2 + P_9^2 + P_{10}^2 = 0 \Rightarrow \quad (9)$$

$$H_{ii} = 1, i = 1, \dots, 10, 13, \dots, 18;$$

$$H_{113} = H_{214} = H_{315} = H_{416} = H_{517} = H_{618} = -1.$$

Finally, orthotropy of **A** and **D** can be respectively stated by, see again [12] or [13],

$$I(P_k) = (P_5 - P_6)^2 = \bar{K} \frac{\pi^2}{16}, \quad \bar{K} = 0, 1 \Rightarrow H_{55} = H_{66} = 1; \quad H_{56} = -1; \quad (10)$$

$$I(P_k) = (P_{17} - P_{18})^2 = \tilde{K} \frac{\pi^2}{16}, \quad \tilde{K} = 0, 1 \Rightarrow H_{1717} = H_{1818} = 1; \quad H_{1718} = -1. \quad (11)$$

This approach lets the designer to chose the type of orthotropy, [12], but if $K=1$ the solution does not correspond with the absolute minimum of the objective function $I(P_k)$.

To end this section, we remark that a feature of the method is the ease of combining each one of the above statements, and more else, with other ones to get new composed properties.

THE GENETIC ALGORITHM BIANCA

In our approach to the formulation of laminate design problems involving stiffness properties, we are inspired to a principle of the greatest generality, that is to say we consider all required properties as design objectives without any priority to some of them, and we develop a unique formulation to take into account any required combination of different design problems. The same need of generality leads to our choice of the resolution method, in

order to conceive a versatile instrument for the design of composite laminates which can adapt to both engineering and academic exigencies.

First of all, the resolution method need to be numeric and suitable to the kind of problem formulation that we propose, that is to say the research of the absolute minima of function $I(P_k)$, which is non-convex when ply orientations are considered among design variables. To solve similar kind of laminate design problems, some authors apply classic optimization algorithms, based on the deepest descent principle [1, 11]. Nevertheless, as the basic gradient algorithm is not very suitable to deal with non-convexity, it is necessary to introduce some relevant modifications which make calculations longer and less efficient.

Moreover, we consider that another important feature of our resolution method has to be the possibility to choose different sets of design variables according to design needs. Of course, design variables can be any characteristic parameters of a composite laminate: orientation angles, stacking sequence, number of plies, material(s) of plies.

Concerning the nature of design variable, a consideration more arises about the variability domains: laminate design variables may be continuous, discrete or grouped, according to different design conditions. For instance, the designer may want to choose orientation angles belonging to the continuous set $[0^\circ, 180^\circ]$, or to the integer set of values $\alpha \in [0^\circ, 180^\circ]$, or to a discrete set of fixed values $[\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n]$. The same consideration is true for the choice of the ply material; but in addition, ply material represents a grouped variable, because it involves the whole set of mechanical properties of the ply, such as elastic modules, strength properties, etc.

For all these reasons, it appears to us that genetic algorithms are suitable methods to apply in order to solve laminate design problems.

In its standard form, a genetic algorithm is an exploring technique based on the rules of natural selection, Darwin's principle of survival of the fittest individuals leading to a constant evolution toward fitter generations [15].

A genetic algorithm treats an initial random population of individuals, which are points belonging to the search space, by classifying them on the scale of their fitness function, that is a measure of their matching to the desired objective. Then, the algorithm sorts pairs of individuals-points (selection), that will take part into the next step, reproduction. In the standard genetic algorithm, the reproduction process involves two operators, cross-over and mutation, which ensure respectively blending and some random changes of genetic characters belonging to the parent population, in order to give the birth to a new generation. By generating a number of new populations, the mean fitness is improved up to achieve an optimum, that is to say a solution to our problem.

The main differences between genetic algorithms and gradient methods are the adequate combination of random and determinist decisions in the selection and reproduction steps, as well as the use of a population of search points instead of a unique search point. These features ensure the efficiency of genetic algorithms in the exploration of non-convex optimization problems.

Moreover, genetic algorithms are specially fit to deal with discrete variables because of the classic technique used to represent individual genetic characters, which is based on a binary coding in order to mimic the natural structure of DNA and to ensure a better exploration of the search space [15].

Hence, we developed the genetic algorithm BIANCA (Bio ANalyse de Composites Assemblés) to solve laminate design problems. BIANCA has the structure of a standard genetic algorithm improved by the introduction of elitism, which is a classic genetic operator [15]. Nevertheless, it shows some innovating features concerning the representation of laminates, the variable coding as well as the treatment of constraints problems. The result is an original and versatile design instrument, that can deal with a great number of different

elastic problems for composite laminates. For a detailed description of the structure of BIANCA, see [12] and [16].

As an input to BIANCA, we specify:

- design objectives;
- constraints (if necessary);
- all parameters which are design variables, as well as their variability domains;
- all fixed parameters, which are considered as constant during a calculation process;
- a condition to stop genetic evolution, that is to say to assess the achievement of a solution to our problem.

Possible design objectives for BIANCA are:

- a. for in-plane and/or bending behaviors:
 1. orthotropy (different shapes, corresponding to $K = 0$ or $K = 1$);
 2. R_0 -orthotropy (polar parameter R_0 is zero);
 3. square-symmetry (polar parameter R_1 is zero);
 4. isotropy;
- b. for coupling between in-plane and bending behaviors:
 1. uncoupling;
- c. for relative shapes of in-plane and bending behaviors:
 1. coincidence of in-plane and bending behaviors ($\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{O}$);
 2. coincidence of in-plane and bending orthotropy axes;
 3. generally, coincidence of in-plane and bending symmetry axes.

All possible combinations of problems listed above can be design objectives for BIANCA, too.

Constraints to the optimization problem can eventually be imposed, in order to search laminates with given elastic in-plane and/or bending rigidities. In BIANCA, we can express constraint conditions on Young modules in the form:

$$\bar{E}_{\max} \geq E_1 ; \bar{E}_{\min} \geq e_1 ; \text{ and/or: } \tilde{E}_{\max} \geq E_2 ; \tilde{E}_{\min} \geq e_2 . \quad (12)$$

In BIANCA, designers can choose laminate design variables among:

- ply orientation angles, δ_k ;
- ply materials.

Their variability domains can be different, as shown in Table 1.

DESIGN PARAMETERS		
ANGLES δ_k	MATERIAL	
	FIXED	VARIABLE
1. δ_k real, $\delta_k \in]-90^\circ, 90^\circ[$;	1. material m_i belonging to a given data-base ;	ply material can be chosen in a set of n_{mat} materials belonging to a given data-base.
2. δ_k real, $\delta_k \in [\alpha, \beta]$;	2. material m defined by the set of its elastic modules ;	
3. $\delta_k \in [\alpha, \beta]$; δ_k discrete values equally spaced by step p_{angle} and $\alpha, \beta \in]-90^\circ, 90^\circ[$;	3. no material is defined ;	
4. $\delta_k \in [\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_{n_{angle}}]$ α_i any values.	4. a material characterized only by its elastic symmetries.	

Table 1 : Definition of laminate design parameters in BIANCA.

From Table 1, we see that generally we choose orientation angles as variables, while ply material can be a variable or a fixed parameter, or even it can be not a parameter at all; in this case, solutions found by BIANCA are valid for any ply material. Moreover, we see that we can define variables on continuous or discrete domains.

Concerning the number of plies n , it is still a fixed parameter in BIANCA, that is to say designer can choose it at the beginning of each calculation.

Once the design conditions defined, BIANCA builds up the initial population, which is a group of randomly sorted laminates. Figure 1 shows the genetic equivalence in BIANCA.

Figure 1. Genetic equivalence in BIANCA.

In BIANCA, a laminate is an individual with n chromosomes (n is the number of plies). Each chromosome is composed of two genes, one for the orientation angle and the other one for the ply material.

Each gene can be active or not in the genetic process, whether the corresponding parameter is a design variable or a fixed one. In BIANCA, cross-over acts on each active gene to ensure a larger blending of genetic characters in the reproduction process; this is an original characteristics, as genetic algorithms for design of composite laminates generally treat the laminate stacking sequence as an unique gene [17].

To end this short presentation of the genetic algorithm BIANCA, we describe the technique we developed to handle constraints in laminate design problems. Once again, our purpose is the respect of the greatest generality, in order to limit the designer interventions; for instance, we wish to avoid the need for the designer to define special program parameters, in order to adapt the algorithm to deal with different design conditions. For this reason, we could not adopt classic methods to handle constraints in genetic algorithms [15, 17].

Our technique, called evolutive method, is based on two basic principles:

- constraints level is progressively and automatically increased during genetic calculations starting from an initial value up to the actual value defined by designer, mimicking the evolution of environmental conditions and an increasing selection pressure;
- individuals that do not respect the actual constraint level are eliminated (*death penalty*) and replaced with acceptable individuals.

As we can see, the evolutive method respects the evolution laws ruling genetic algorithms.

EXAMPLES OF SOLUTIONS FOUND BY BIANCA

Using BIANCA, we treated a large number of different design problems (different objectives, different design variables, active or inactive constraints, etc.) and we found a lot of solutions for each. We give here some examples of results obtained by BIANCA in order to show the large set of design conditions to which BIANCA is successfully applied (see Table 2).

	Design objectives	Ply	Orientation angles variability domain	n	N	p	f	Example of solution found (°)
1	In- and out-of plane orthotropy ($K=0$), coincidence of axes and uncoupling	any material]-90°, 90°]	10	200	500	2.53×10^{-5}	[0/-17.16/-2.69/5.05/-14.60/-5.97/-14.45/5.34/1.65/-12.95]
2	Orthotropy : $K=1$ for A and $K=0$ for D, coincidence of axes and uncoupling	any material]-90°, 90°]	12	200	500	4.74×10^{-5}	[0/44.67/15.70/-39.98/-25.46/-37.21/59.04/54.28/36.92/-38.16/18.58/-5.23]
3	Orthotropy : $K=1$ for A and $K=0$ for D, coincidence of axes and uncoupling	any material]-90°, 90°], $p_{angle}=10^\circ$	12	200	300	5.08×10^{-4}	[0/10/40/-40/-20/50/-20/30/-40/30/10/-10]
4	In-plane isotropy, bending orthotropy ($K=0$), uncoupling	any material]-90°, 90°]	12	200	500	9.40×10^{-6}	[0/75.99/-31.45/-67.48/37.97/31.97/-38.49/-76.87/57.69/89.31/14.15/-23.88]
5	In-plane isotropy, bending orthotropy ($K=0$), uncoupling	any material]-90°, 90°], $p_{angle}=10^\circ$	12	200	500	1.13×10^{-4}	[0/60/70/10/-60/-50/-60/-50/60/0/10/70]
6	In-plane square-symmetry and quasi-homogeneity	any material]-90°, 90°]	12	1000	4000	2.27×10^{-5}	[0/62.46/-53.44/81.56/-15.80/-75.75/66.59/0/-0.54/46.07/-28.12/-88.94]
7	Full isotropy	any material]-90°, 90°]	12	2000	3000	3.46×10^{-4}	[0/51.58/-51.49/85.83/-51.34/85.04/24.09/-19.08/30.94/-11.16/63.28/-65.21]
8	In-plane isotropy, bending orthotropy ($K=0$) and uncoupling	Data-base: UD carbone/epoxyde T300/5208	{0°, ±45°, 90°}	12	500	250	4.55×10^{-4}	[0/90/-45/45/90/45/-45/0/-45/45/90/0]
9	Orthotropy : $K=1$ for A and $K=0$ for D, coincidence of axes and uncoupling Constraints on in-plane modules: $E_{max} > 100\text{Gpa}$, $E_{min} > 50\text{Gpa}$.	Data-base: UD carbone/epoxyde T300/5208]-90°, 90°], $p_{angle}=15^\circ$	12	400	50	1.3×10^{-3} $E_{max}=156.1\text{ Gpa}$ $E_{min}=51.2\text{ Gpa}$	[0/30/-15/15/90/-75/0/45/-75/0/-15/15]

Table 2. Examples of solutions obtained by BIANCA (N : population size; p : number of generations; f : value of the objective function associated to the given solution)

We observe that BIANCA can solve design problems with orientation angles defined as continuous or discrete variables, taking non-standard or standard values (for instance, see example n°. 8, Table 2).

Figures 2 and 3 show polar curves of in-plane and bending Young modules concerning laminates of examples 8 and 9.

Figure 2. Young modules for laminate of example n°. 8.

Figure 3. Young modules for laminate of example n°. 9.

Finally, Figures 4 and 5 show respectively the convergence of the objective function concerning example n°. 8 (we remember that exact solutions correspond to zeros of the objective function) and the evolution of constraints level for calculations in example n°. 9.

Figure 4. Convergence of the objective function in example n°. 8.

Figure 5. Evolution of in-plane Young modules subject to constraints in example n°. 9.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we propose an innovating approach to composite laminate design problems, which combines a theoretical formulation based on the polar representation method of plane elasticity and a genetic algorithm as a resolution technique.

Using polar method [11], we found a link of physical coherence for a large number of elastic design objectives, and we could express them in terms of minimization of a function $I(P_k)$, that is to say in the form of a classic optimization problem [12-13]. Our theoretical formulation is a general one, as we take into account no simplifying hypothesis.

Then, we developed an adequate instrument to solve laminate design problems, that is to say the genetic algorithm BIANCA.

In this paper, we described the structure of BIANCA and we pointed out its innovating features concerning the representation of design variables and the technique to handle design constraints. Generally, BIANCA is a versatile software which can deal with a large range of different design problems corresponding to different design conditions and exigencies. In particular, BIANCA is conceived to fit engineering as well as academic problems.

We gave a great number of results obtained by BIANCA, and we put a special attention to the convergence behavior of the genetic algorithm, which is a robust and efficient technique to solve laminate design problems.

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